

Wine yeast selections in the Iberian Peninsula: *Saccharomyces* and non-*Saccharomyces* as drivers of innovation in Spanish and Portuguese wine industries

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40 **Abstract**

41

42 Continuous innovations have accompanied the evolution of wine production in the last
43 decades from the vineyard to the bottle; among these, a crucial role is played by wine
44 yeasts. The Iberian Peninsula includes several wine-producing areas of great relevance,
45 and this work presents the first comprehensive review of relevant yeast selections from
46 both Spain and Portugal. Yeast selection for the wine industry started in 1950 in Spain to
47 understand the microbial ecology associated with grapes and wineries and select the
48 optimal strains to improve the performances of alcoholic fermentation and the overall
49 wine quality. This process of characterization has been strongly developed over the last
50 30 years, firstly on *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, and, lately, with intense activity on the
51 heterogenous and promising category of non-*Saccharomyces*. Several thousand yeast
52 strains have been isolated, identified by biochemical and molecular techniques and tested
53 to select those with better performance and/or specific technological properties. The
54 present review proposes a global survey of this massive *ex-situ* preservation of eukaryotic
55 microorganisms, a reservoir of biotechnological solutions for the wine sector,
56 overviewing relevant screenings that led to the selection of yeast strains from 12 genera
57 and 22 species of oenological significance. In the first part, the attention goes to the
58 selection programmes related to relevant wine-producing areas of the Iberia Peninsula
59 (i.e. Douro, Extremadura, Galicia, La Mancha and Uclés, Ribera del Duero, Rioja, Sherry
60 area, and Valencia). In the second part, the focus shifted on specific non-*Saccharomyces*
61 genera/species selected from different Spanish and Portuguese regions, exploited to
62 enhance particular attributes of the final wines. *A fil rouge* of the dissertation is the design
63 of tailored biotechnological solutions for wines typical of given geographic areas. The
64 review covers the impact of yeast selection for regional high-quality wine productions in
65 the Iberian Peninsula, offering a new point of view to summarise the relevance of yeast
66 as bioresources for the wine industry.

67

68 **Keywords:** wine, yeast, Spain, Portugal, *Saccharomyces*, non-*Saccharomyces*,
69 *Lachancea*, *Schizosaccharomyces*, *Hanseniaspora*, quality

70

71 Introduction

72
73 The Iberian Peninsula is a geographic region of extreme interest for wine production.
74 Together with Italy and France, Spain is among the leading world wine producers.
75 Portugal has a dynamic wine industry with well-recognised products at the global level.
76 Yeast selection is a crucial driver of product and process innovation to improve wine
77 safety and quality (Berbegal et al., 2016). In the past, most of the screenings were
78 dedicated to *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* species (Pretorius, 2000) and lately, the focus
79 includes the selection of non-*Saccharomyces* to improve sensory quality, stability and
80 wine freshness (Morata et al., 2020). The normal distribution of yeasts in grape skins
81 shows a high prevalence of non-*Saccharomyces* yeasts, particularly in grapes damaged
82 by different sorts of rot. Indeed, health status is the main driving force shaping the
83 microbiota of grape berries (Barata et al., 2012). Selection of *Saccharomyces* strains is
84 based on global effects of yeasts on colour, aroma, structure, and general parameters, such
85 as fermentative power, fermentation kinetics, tolerance to ethanol, tolerance to extreme
86 fermentation temperatures, production of low volatile acidity, low requirements of Yeast
87 Assimilable Nitrogen, resistance to SO₂, and desired killer phenotypes (Pretorius, 2000;
88 Suárez-Lepe & Morata, 2012). All crucial parameters to ensure the correct course of
89 alcoholic fermentation. These properties are also considered for selecting non-
90 *Saccharomyces*, even if their contribution is generally evaluated as incremental for the
91 sensory modulations and fundamental for the solution of specific technological aptitudes.
92 Non-*Saccharomyces* have a huge potential in producing compounds that can influence
93 wine sensory properties (Tufariello et al., 2021). From a technological point of view,
94 selected non-*Saccharomyces* strains can be suitable for high alcohol content wines, with
95 increased production of glycerine and low alcohol rate (*Starmerella bacillaris*, *Candida*
96 *stellata*), degradation of malic acid (*Schizosaccharomyces pombe*), low volatile acidity
97 (*Torulaspota delbrueckii*), biocontrol of spoilage microbes (*Metschnikowia*
98 *pulcherrima*), acidification and low production of medium-chain fatty acids (*Lachancea*
99 *thermotolerans*) (Hranilovic et al., 2021; Roudil et al., 2019). As for saccharomycetes,
100 the biotechnological potential of non-*Saccharomyces* is in continuous
101 exploration/characterization, in terms of species and desired properties for oenological
102 applications. For example, the organic acid production by some non-*Saccharomyces* may
103 also be reflected in higher flavour persistence that is regarded as an attribute of fine wines
104 (Malfeito-Ferreira, 2021).

105 In the Iberian Peninsula, wine yeast selection was developed early by Íñigo at the
106 beginning of the second half of the XX century and subsequent work by Suárez-Lepe
107 selecting yeasts at the Institute of Industrial fermentations (IFI-CSIC) (Suárez-Lepe &
108 Íñigo Leal, 1990). Selection procedures have been developed in several Iberian wine
109 regions, but no review paper summarises the efforts of yeast strains isolation,
110 characterization and exploitation from this vast geographical area deserved of particular
111 interest for wine production. This work proposes a number of case studies to exemplify
112 the relevance of tailored selection programmes in terms of regional high-quality wines
113 productions and yeast valorization as bioresources for the Iberian wine industry. On the
114 one hand, it is proposed an examination of studies related to the following relevant wine-
115 producing areas of the Iberia Peninsula: Galicia (northwest), Extremadura (west), Douro
116 (west), Ribera del Duero (northwest), Rioja (north), Sherry area (south-west), Valencia
117 (east), La Mancha and Uclés (centre) (Figure 1). On the other hand, the review offers an

118 overview of specific non-*Saccharomyces* genera/species (Figure 2) selected from
119 different Spanish and Portuguese regions exploited to enhance particular attributes of the
120 final wines.

121

122 **Yeast selection in “DO Ribera del Guadiana” (Extremadura, Spain)**

123

124 The first attempt to isolate wine yeasts from Extremadura comes from the early 1990s.
125 An outstanding screening of yeasts isolated from spontaneous must fermentations
126 thorough the wineries of DO Ribera del Guadiana was done, and a new method for wine
127 yeast selection was designed considering the particular oenological characteristics of this
128 warm region (Regodón et al., 1997). Several *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* strains were
129 selected (such as JP73, JP85, and JP88; Table 1). These yeasts showed interesting
130 technological characteristics such as resistance to SO₂, killer phenotype, growth at high
131 temperature, low foam production, low volatile acidity, high ethanol concentration, and
132 low residual sugars in the wine. One of these yeasts was patented (JP88), and it is still
133 produced and marketed for commercial winemaking. Notwithstanding this, an efficient
134 method to easily monitor these yeasts in the winery was missing. It was required to ensure
135 that the inoculated yeast really conducted the fermentation process. This method had to
136 be simple and inexpensive for application in commercial wineries. Spontaneous mutants
137 resistant to cycloheximide (cyh^R) were isolated from the selected wine yeasts (such as
138 JP73R and JP85R; Table 1). The *cynR* mutations did not affect the fermentation kinetics
139 and wine quality or the viability of active dry yeast made with these mutants. A fast,
140 reliable, and economical method to monitor inoculated selected yeast through must
141 fermentation was developed using these mutants (F. Pérez et al., 2000). ~~We use this~~
142 ~~method~~ confirm the dominance of inoculated cyh^R yeasts in commercial wine
143 fermentation. As the use of these mutants during consecutive years could make them
144 resident yeasts in the wineries, alternative methods were designed to alternate the use of
145 different yeast mutants and genetic markers in different vintages. This can avoid the
146 background of resident yeasts in the test to monitor inoculated selected yeasts. The new
147 tests were based on *S. cerevisiae* spontaneous mutants resistant to sulfometuron (SMR10-
148 11D and SMR16-5A) and rhodamine 6B (such as RhodM2H3-1B and RhodM2H5-6D)
149 (Table 1). These yeasts are easy to detect at the winery by replica-plate or colour-plate
150 assay (Ambrona et al., 2005, 2006). Additionally, some of these genetically marked
151 yeasts were further genetically improved by elimination of recessive growth-retarding
152 alleles followed by spore-clone selection or followed by crossing with selected killer wine
153 yeasts (Ramírez et al., 1999, 2004). As a complementary option, IME1 gene was deleted
154 in some yeast strains to avoid meiotic sporulation and spreading of inoculated commercial
155 yeasts in nature (such as E324; Table 1) (Ramírez & Ambrona, 2008). Although some of
156 the above-selected yeasts were already killer K2 type, their killer capability was not very
157 intense in the environmental conditions of sparkling-wine second fermentation held in
158 glass bottles (low pH and temperature). New killer Klus types (such as EX198 and
159 EX229; Table 1) were then isolated and selected to increase yeast autolysis during second
160 fermentation and ageing of cava wines (Rodríguez-Cousiño et al., 2011). These yeasts
161 showed killer activity at pH 3 and 12 °C, and good fermentation performance under high
162 CO₂ pressure (>6 atm). In parallel, new killer-sensitive slow-growth yeasts (such as
163 Rod23-1B; Table 1) were selected to be killed by Klus yeast when inoculated in the
164 sparkling-wine second fermentation. This strategy increased yeast dead and autolysis and

165 improved wine quality (Velázquez et al., 2016). Last attempts to select wine yeast from
166 Extremadura are mainly focused on non-conventional yeasts. New *Torulaspota*
167 *delbrueckii* killer strains (such as EX1180 and EX1257; Table 1) were isolated for
168 winemaking (Ramírez et al., 2015). They killed *S. cerevisiae* yeasts and were able to
169 dominate and complete the fermentation of the sterile must. Sequential yeast inoculation
170 of white must with *T. delbrueckii* followed by *S. cerevisiae* did not ensure *T. delbrueckii*
171 dominance or wine quality improvement. However, single inoculation of non-sterile must
172 at high cell concentrations allowed the *T. delbrueckii* killer strains to dominate and
173 complete the must fermentation to reach above 11% ethanol, but it was not possible when
174 inoculating non-killer strains. Interestingly, the *T. delbrueckii*-dominated wines showed
175 nice and unusual dried fruit/pastry aromas (Velázquez et al., 2015). These killer strains
176 also dominated the fermentation of crushed red grapes when they were single-inoculated.
177 They reached above 14% ethanol, and they promoted malolactic fermentation that was
178 absent in the *S. cerevisiae* wines made side by side. Again, the *T. delbrueckii* wines
179 showed dried-fruit/pastry aromas, raising the organoleptic quality and rendering wines
180 with excellent aroma complexity, mouth-feel, and sweetness (Ramírez et al., 2016). The
181 usefulness of these killer yeasts for sparkling-wine making has also been analysed.
182 Unfortunately, the foaming capacity of *T. delbrueckii* base wines was very low compared
183 to *S. cerevisiae* base wines, and the organoleptic quality of the *T. delbrueckii* base wines
184 was judged inappropriate for sparkling-wine making. However, the organoleptic quality
185 of the mixed-inoculated sparkling wines was better than that of wines single-inoculated
186 with *S. cerevisiae* and showed no deterioration of foam quality (Velázquez et al., 2019).
187 As *T. delbrueckii* has lower efficiency in completing wine fermentation than conventional
188 yeast *S. cerevisiae*, new strains with enhanced resistance to winemaking conditions were
189 obtained (greater resistance to SO₂, ethanol, and CO₂ pressure). Most of these killer
190 strains showed better capability for base wine fermentation than the parental strain (such
191 as Td-MutHP41 and Td-MutHP42; Table 1); and some of them approached the
192 fermentation capability of *S. cerevisiae* (Velázquez et al., 2020).

193 194 **Yeasts isolated in Douro (Portugal) for biological deacetication of musts and wines**

195
196 The ability of yeasts to catabolize acetic acid can be particularly exploited to develop
197 methods for the zymological deacidification of grape-musts or wines once fermentative
198 yeasts can metabolize acetic acid during a refermentation process. Unusually high
199 concentrations of acetic acid can be removed from wines by this biological method which
200 consists in adding one-third of an acidic wine with two-thirds of freshly crushed grapes
201 or of the residual marc from the fermentation of finished wine, such that the volatile
202 acidity of this mixture does not exceed 0.73 g/L of acetic acid. This rather empirical
203 methodology reduces volatile acidity to values close to 0.37 g/L of acetic acid and implies
204 low costs (Vilela-Moura et al., 2011; Zoecklein et al., 1995). Yeasts can use acetate as a
205 sole carbon and energy source to generate energy and cellular biomass under aerobic
206 conditions (Schüller, 2003; Vilela-Moura et al., 2011). Having this yeast feature in mind,
207 Vilela and collaborators, in 2008, isolated several yeast strains (*Saccharomyces* and non-
208 *Saccharomyces*) in Wallerstein Laboratory Nutrient Agar (WL) medium from
209 refermentation processes of acidic wines, at winery scale (Figure 4A). Among these
210 isolates, 135 were tested for their ability to consume acetic acid in the presence of glucose,
211 using a differential medium developed by Schuller et al. (Schuller et al., 2000) containing
212 acetic acid and glucose. Four isolates - strains 30C, 43C, 44C, and 45C (Figure 54) (Table

213 1) were obtained in this medium and were further identified by the amplification of the
214 D1–D2 variable domain at the 5' end of the 26S rDNA (nucleotides 63–642 for *S.*
215 *cerevisiae*) with primers NL-1 and NL-4 and the amplified fragments were subsequently
216 sequenced. Sequence similarity search was done using GenBank BLASTN search. D1–
217 D2 sequence of strain 30C, 43C, and 45C showed 99–100% identity with deposited *S.*
218 *cerevisiae* sequences. D1–D2 sequence of strain 44C shows 99% identity with *Lachancea*
219 *thermotolerans* NRRL Y-8284, a strain like the type of strain of *Zygosaccharomyces*
220 *thermotolerans*, isolated from mirabelle plum and identified by Lachance (Lachance,
221 1998). Until October 2004, this species was considered as *Kluyveromyces*
222 *thermotolerans*. Later, the effect of glucose and acetic acid concentrations and aeration
223 conditions on acetic acid consumption by *S. cerevisiae* strains 30C, 43C, and 45C and by
224 *L. thermotolerans* 44C was studied at a laboratory scale. The strain *Z. bailii* ISA1307 was
225 used as a reference strain. The results showed that *L. thermotolerans* 44C was able to
226 degrade 28.2% of the initial acid when grown under limited aerobic conditions in a mixed
227 substrate medium which contained glucose (5.0%, w/v) and acetic acid (5.0 g L⁻¹), while
228 30C only degraded 2%, 43C – 4.6% and 45C – 5.8% (Vilela-Moura et al., 2008). To
229 verify the potential application of the three best-performing strains (43C, 44C and 45C)
230 in refermentation processes, under wine cellar conditions, the strains were inoculated in
231 a mixed medium containing two-thirds of minimal medium (van Uden, 1967),
232 supplemented with one-third of an acidic white wine, being the volatile acidity of the
233 mixture 1.13 g L⁻¹ of acetic acid. Two wine-supplemented mineral media (Table 2) were
234 tested: The 1st simulated the refermentation of wine with freshly crushed grapes or with
235 grape-must [13% glucose (w/v), 4% ethanol (v/v)]; the 2nd simulated the refermentation
236 of wine with the residual marc from a finished wine fermentation [3.3% glucose (w/v),
237 10% ethanol (v/v)]. Acetic acid consumption was again evaluated under aerobic or limited
238 aerobic conditions to assess whether aeration was a limiting factor in the process. Once it
239 was known that higher glucose concentration levels could lead to a decreased glucose
240 consumption rate, the rate of acetic acid and glucose consumption was evaluated at the
241 end of 48 and 72 h for the first and second medium, respectively (Vilela-Moura et al.,
242 2008). *L. thermotolerans* 44C was efficient in terms of acetic acid consumption in the
243 high-glucose medium and aerobic conditions, as 94.8% of the initial acetic acid was
244 consumed (Table 2). However, the efficiency of *L. thermotolerans* 44C in acetic acid
245 consumption decreased significantly in the high-glucose concentration medium under
246 limited aerobic conditions, as only 15.3% of the initial acetic acid was consumed (Vilela-
247 Moura et al., 2008), as shown in Table 2. Interestingly, *S. cerevisiae* 43C and 45C showed
248 the ability to reduce 37.5% and 40.1%, respectively, of the initial acetic acid, in low
249 glucose medium and under limited aerobic conditions. These features make these three
250 strains and interesting bio tool to be used in the biological deacetication of musts and
251 wines.

252

253 **Yeast selection in Galicia**

254

255 Yeasts were isolated from must samples and during spontaneous fermentations from
256 traditional cultivars in Galicia carried out in the experimental winery of *Estación de*
257 *Viticultura e Enoloxía de Galicia* (Evega-Agacal). *Saccharomyces* and non-
258 *Saccharomyces* yeasts were distinguished by growth on Lysine medium. *S. cerevisiae*
259 isolates were characterised at the strain level by analysis of mitochondrial DNA
260 restriction profiles (mtDNA-RFLPs) (Querol et al., 1992). Non-*Saccharomyces* were
261 isolated from natural fermentations of musts from different Denominations of Origin in
262 Galicia. WL Nutrient Agar allowed distinguishing among certain wine yeast species

263 based on their colony morphotype. Based on their aspect, representative colonies from
264 each sample were isolated on YPD for further characterisation at the genetic level. The
265 isolates were identified at species level by PCR amplification of the 5.8S rRNA gene
266 (Esteve-Zarzoso et al., 1999). Yeast identity was confirmed by PCR amplification and
267 sequencing of D1/D2 region of 26S rDNA gene as described by Kurtzman and Robnett,
268 (Kurtzman & Robnett, 1998). Preliminary studies on the enological potential of yeast
269 were carried out at the laboratory scale using pasteurized must. The fermentative power,
270 ethanol yield, volatile acidity, sugar consumption and production of lactic acid were
271 evaluated. In addition, the killer activity and SH₂ production were determined for
272 *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* strains. The best-scored strains were evaluated at
273 microvinification scale in the experimental winery of E Vega, including fermentation
274 ability, implantation, and their influence on chemical and sensory characteristics of wine.
275 The results obtained at microvinification and pilot scale in the experimental winery of
276 E Vega highlighted the properties of *S. cerevisiae* XG3 (Table 1). This strain showed a
277 good fermentative ability and successfully completed the fermentation. Analysis by
278 mtDNA-RFLPs of randomly isolated colonies revealed that XG3 was able to overgrow
279 the wild population in the must and lead the fermentations where it was inoculated, being
280 the dominant strain (implantation frequencies > 89%). At the chemical level, XG3
281 produces more esters and long-chain fatty acids compared to other native or commercial
282 strains. The wines elaborated with XG3 achieved higher scores in sensory analysis than
283 those elaborated with commercial and/or other native strains. Due to its positive
284 contribution to wine characteristics, *S. cerevisiae* XG3 was produced as active dry yeast
285 and applied at the industrial scale in several wineries (Blanco, Vázquez-Alén, et al., 2021)
286 (Table 1). The fermentation kinetics of XG3 vinifications was similar to commercial ones,
287 although the required time to complete fermentation was vintage and winery dependent.
288 *S. cerevisiae* XG3 showed an acceptable implantation ability (>90% in all fermentations).
289 The wines from XG3 tended to have higher total acidity and lower alcohol content than
290 control wines from commercial starters. In addition, their volatile composition differed
291 from control wines. However, lower differences were appreciated at the sensory level,
292 where the panellists in XG3 wines perceive fruity and floral descriptors. Preliminary
293 assays at laboratory scale, including 60 strains from several yeast species, evidenced their
294 limitations to complete fermentation. For example, when used as monoculture,
295 *Metschnikowia* spp., *H. uvarum*, and *Candida* spp., produced wines with 6.5% alcoholic
296 degree containing >150 g/L of sugars, whereas wines obtained with *L. thermotolerans*,
297 *K. dobzhanskii*, *T. delbrueckii*, *Starm. bacillaris* o *Zygosaccharomyces* spp. reached 12%
298 of alcohol, but they still have sugars to consume. A representative strain of each species
299 was chosen, and its potential contribution to the chemical composition of wines was
300 evaluated in sequential fermentations with a commercial *S. cerevisiae* strain to ensure
301 fermentation completion. The results evidenced the limited fermentative power of these
302 yeasts and the differences in their survival after the addition of *S. cerevisiae* to complete
303 fermentation. Some strains reduced the alcohol and/or increased the total acidity of the
304 wine. The positive effect on sensory wine properties as well as the production of desirable
305 volatile compounds were confirmed for *Metschnikowia* spp. (Mf278 and Mp176),
306 *Lachancea thermotolerans* Lt93 and *Pichia kluyveri* Pk188 (Blanco, Castrillo, et al.,
307 2021).

308 **Yeast Selection in la D.O.Ca. Rioja**

310
311 In the D.O.Ca. Rioja, three yeast selection programmes have been conducted. The first
312 two within the species *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* for the management of alcoholic

313 fermentation in white and red wines, respectively, and the last within the group of non-
314 *Saccharomyces* yeasts.

315 The first selection programme was carried out between 1990 and 1994 and concluded
316 with the commercialisation in 1997 of the first indigenous yeast from the D.O.Ca. Rioja.
317 This yeast has been marketed internationally by the Lallemand company under the name
318 Uvaferm VRB from 1997 to the present. The selection programme was developed from
319 the vinification of white and rosé wines made in an experimental winery with grapes from
320 different subzones of the D.O.Ca. Rioja during the 1990 harvest. Three hundred isolates
321 were obtained, 245 of which belonged to the species *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. The
322 objective of this first selection programme was to obtain inoculums in order to manage
323 the fermentation of white wines. This fact may attract attention since La Rioja is a region
324 known especially for its red wines. But in those years, inoculation was not a general
325 practice for controlling fermentation, and it was seen more as a tool to solve fermentation
326 problems, which were more frequent in the production of white wines. From 245
327 *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* isolates, successive selection stages were performed: killer
328 phenotype, degree of flocculation, production of hydrogen sulphide, resistance to sulphur,
329 microvinifications in synthetic must and the physicochemical characteristics of wines
330 made from grape must. After that, seven strains were selected, and with them, the last
331 selection stage was undertaken. For this, small-scale vinifications were carried out in an
332 experimental winery, studying the wines obtained from a physicochemical, aromatic and
333 organoleptic point of view. To monitor the inoculated strains in the tanks, the mtDNA
334 restriction analysis method was used after comparing it with other techniques available
335 for this purpose. (Gutiérrez, López, Santamaría, et al., 1997). The selected strain was
336 characterised by having a neutral phenotype with respect to the killer factor, high
337 tolerance to ethanol, a short lag phase, good fermentation kinetics and an optimal
338 fermentation temperature range of between 15 and 30 °C. This yeast produces little foam,
339 sulphur and short-chain fatty acids, enhances the varietal character and facilitates the
340 development of malolactic fermentation. (Gutiérrez, 1995; Gutiérrez, López, &
341 Santamaría, 1997; López et al., 1999). For all these reasons, this strain is currently being
342 used in wineries for the fermentation of both white and red wines.

343 At the end of the 1990s, the inoculation of the vats with active dry yeasts began to become
344 more widespread, not only in the production of white wines but also in that of red wines.
345 On this occasion, the isolation of the strains was carried out in situ in 16 wineries
346 distributed throughout the D.O.Ca. Rioja that had never used commercial yeasts. Samples
347 were taken during four consecutive harvests (1997-2000), and in each winery, a tank was
348 selected in which samples were taken at three points in time (24 hours of incubation,
349 tumultuous fermentation and end of fermentation). All these samplings allowed us to
350 carry out the selection program and also an extensive ecological study on the diversity of
351 yeasts (Epifanio et al., 1999; Gutiérrez et al., 1999, 2001; López et al., 2006; Santamaría
352 et al., 2005, 2019). For the selection process, we started with 1581 isolates, which, after
353 their identification, generated a collection of 1258 strains of the species *Saccharomyces*
354 *cerevisiae*. These isolates were later identified at the clonal level by means of
355 mitochondrial DNA restriction analysis, giving rise to 553 different clones, with which
356 the selection programme was embarked on. In this case, in addition to the criteria used in
357 the previous programme, other specific criteria for the production of red wines were
358 included, such as the influence of the yeast strain on the colour of the wine (adsorption of
359 anthocyanins by yeast cell walls, production of ethanal, pectolytic and β -glucosidase

360 activities), the influence on malolactic fermentation (degradation of malic acid and
361 nutritional needs) and release of polysaccharides. Finally, the resistance of yeasts to
362 different stress conditions (temperature and concentrations of sulphur, sugar and acetic
363 acid) was studied. As a result, the final phase of the process was undertaken in an
364 experimental cellar with five yeasts, which concluded with the selection of one of them.
365 Before its commercialization in 2007 under the name Zymaflore RJA64, several tests
366 were carried out at an industrial level in which this strain was compared with other strains
367 on the market for the same type of wines. This yeast has a high tolerance to ethanol, an
368 optimum fermentation temperature of between 28 and 32 °C, a low need for nitrogen, and
369 produces minimal volatile acidity. In addition, it forms high amounts of glycerol, has a
370 significant release of polysaccharides, a moderate production of higher alcohols and high
371 formation of esters, which is why its use is recommended to achieve complex and full-
372 bodied wines. (López et al., 2007; Santamaría, 2009).

373 Finally, the third yeast selection process responds to the current interest in improving the
374 characteristics of wine produced by non-*Saccharomyces*. This study aimed to select non-
375 *Saccharomyces* strains as inoculums in producing quality red wines (Escribano-Viana et
376 al., 2021). The work started from a yeast collection created from previous studies on yeast
377 ecology at D.O.Ca. Rioja (Garijo et al., 2008; Ocón et al., 2013a, 2013b; Ocón, **Gutiérrez,**
378 **Garijo, López,** et al., 2010; Ocón, **Gutiérrez, Garijo, Tenorio,** et al., 2010), which was
379 composed of more than 500 strains belonging to 30 different non-*Saccharomyces*.
380 Preselection of the yeasts was done based on two criteria: firstly, species with good
381 fermentation behaviour described by other authors, and secondly, species little-studied
382 but repeatedly identified by our team in oenological ecosystems (*Williopsis pratensis*,
383 *Zygosaccharomyces bailii*, *Candida zeylanoides*). The number of isolates with which the
384 selection process began was 160. We started the work by analysing the genetic diversity
385 within the non-*Saccharomyces* species studied, detecting a high diversity within the.
386 (González-Arenzana et al., 2017). The sulphur resistance of the strains, the killer activity
387 and the possible interactions with other yeasts present in vinifications such as
388 *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Brettanomyces bruxellensis* were also studied.
389 Characteristics such as the presence of enzymatic activities in the isolates (Escribano et
390 al., 2017), their oenological behaviour (Escribano et al., 2018) or their influence on the
391 aromatic (Escribano-Viana et al., 2018) and polyphenolic composition (Escribano-Viana,
392 Portu, et al., 2019) of the wines inoculated with these yeasts have also been evaluated.
393 This work expanded the knowledge of a large number of non-*Saccharomyces* yeast whose
394 oenological interest had not been studied previously. Furthermore, the grape variety has
395 been found to influence the yeast's ability to modulate the characteristics of the wine.
396 (Escribano-Viana, **Garijo,** et al., 2019). The inoculum finally selected in this work is a
397 mixed inoculum made up of *Torulasporea delbrueckii* and *Lachancea thermotolerans*
398 (70/30), which stands out for its ability to increase the acidity of the wine due to the
399 production of lactic acid, a characteristic of great interest in the current context of climate
400 change. It also leads to an increase in the content of glycerol, which can provide the wine
401 with attributes such as smoothness, sweetness and complexity, or ethyl lactate, which
402 provides pleasant aromas. In the wines made with this inoculum, an increase in the
403 content of certain adducts (vitisins) formed with anthocyanins has also been observed,
404 favouring the wine's colour stability. The behaviour of this inoculum is currently being
405 studied on a semi-industrial scale, and the final goal is its commercialization as a mixed
406 inoculum to be used in sequential inoculations with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

407

408 **Selected local yeasts from Denomination of Origin (D.O.) “Vinos de Madrid”**
409 **(Spain)**

410

411 The D.O. “Vinos de Madrid” created in 1990, is located in the center of Spain and covers
412 an area of 8,900 ha. This D.O. comprises 52 wineries in four subzones: Arganda (28),
413 Navalcarnero (5), San Martín de Valdeiglesias (18) and El Molar (1). Although the use
414 of commercial active dry yeasts is a habitual practice in the traditional system of wine
415 elaboration in this D.O., in last years, there has been an increasing interest in the use of
416 local yeasts, particularly in organic production with higher biomass and biodiversity of
417 associated microbiota (Callejon et al., 2010; Cordero-Bueso, Arroyo, Serrano, Tello, et
418 al., 2011; Gil-Díaz et al., 2019). IMIDRA Institute has a large yeast collection established
419 in 1950, including over 3,200 strains from different Spanish regions. Most of these strains
420 have been isolated in numerous ecological studies on spontaneous wine elaborations,
421 vineyards and cellar equipment from D.O. “Vinos de Madrid” between 1990 and 2010
422 (Arroyo et al., 1998; Cabellos et al., 2002; Cordero-Bueso, Arroyo, Serrano, & Valero,
423 2011; Cordero-Bueso, Arroyo, Serrano, Tello, et al., 2011; Gallego et al., 2005; Gil-Díaz,
424 2003; Gil-Díaz et al., 2019; Hidalgo & Flores, 1991; Tello et al., 2012). A classical
425 taxonomic analysis was done to identify *Saccharomyces* and non-*Saccharomyces* yeasts
426 belonging to IMIDRA collection until approximately the year 2000, based on the
427 taxonomic manual of Kreger-van Rij (Kreger van Rij, 1984) and Kurtzman&Fell
428 (Kurtzman et al., 1998). Later, molecular techniques were applied for yeast identification.
429 *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* isolates have been classified at strain level by applying
430 different methods: RAPDs (random amplified polymorphic DNA), CAPs (cleaved
431 amplified polymorphic sequence), AFLPs (amplified fragment length polymorphism),
432 PFGE (pulsed-field gel electrophoresis) and SSRs (simple sequence repeats) (Arroyo,
433 2000; Cordero-Bueso, Arroyo, Serrano, Tello, et al., 2011; Gallego et al., 2005; Gil-Díaz
434 et al., 2019; M. A. Pérez et al., 2001; Tello et al., 2012). During the last years, the SSR
435 method has been chiefly employed by *S. cerevisiae* identification and monitoring to have
436 the greatest discriminatory power and efficiency and to be faster and easier to interpret
437 than the other techniques studied (Gallego et al., 2005; M. A. Pérez et al., 2001). Non-
438 *Saccharomyces* have been distinguished by their growth in Lysine Agar and differential
439 medium WL (Pallman et al., 2001), and their identification was carried out by means of
440 PCR-RFLP of the 5.8S-ITS ribosomal region using the primers ITS1 and ITS4 (Esteve-
441 Zarzoso et al., 1999). Most recently, all selected *Saccharomyces* and non-*Saccharomyces*
442 strains (Table 1) have been confirmed by sequencing of D1/D2 region of the 26S rDNA
443 gen using the primers NL1 and NL4 (Kurtzman & Robnett, 1998). It is well known that
444 native yeasts are better adapted to specific environmental conditions and substrates from
445 their geographical area (Esteve-Zarzoso et al., 2000); also, the increase of knowledge
446 about the native yeast communities present in vineyards and cellars can be useful to give
447 distinctive characteristics to wine (Tello et al., 2012). On the other hand, the use of active
448 dry yeasts does not guarantee their dominance during fermentation. A study of Gil-Díaz
449 et al. (Gil-Díaz et al., 2019) in ten wineries from D.O. “Vinos de Madrid” over two
450 consecutive years concluded that only nine of the thirty fermentations studied were
451 characterized by a successful implantation level using *S. cerevisiae* commercial yeasts.
452 Therefore, autochthonous yeast selection is an important goal for Madrid wines' diversity,
453 typicity, and quality.

454 Regarding to *S. cerevisiae* strains (Table 1), *S. cerevisiae* CLI 889, a native yeast isolated
455 from Airén (*Vitis vinifera* L. cv.) must fermentation in 1994, is well-known and widely
456 tested at IMIDRA laboratories. This yeast strain has been selected by its high fermentative
457 power and optimal implantation rate, resistance to ethanol, low production of acetic acid,
458 hydrogen sulfide and sulfur dioxide, high acidity and fruity and fresh character (Arroyo,
459 2000; Cordero-Bueso et al., 2016); and also, it was proposed as the best candidate to co-
460 starter cultures together with non-*Saccharomyces* (Cordero-Bueso et al., 2016). Several
461 studies have been done at laboratory and pilot scale where the presence of *S. cerevisiae*
462 CLI 889 has ensured the completion of fermentation and produced more complex wines
463 in mixed or sequential elaborations with different native non-*Saccharomyces* strains
464 (García, Apolinar-Valiente, et al., 2017; García, Arroyo, et al., 2017; García, Esteve-
465 Zarzoso, et al., 2017). As previously mentioned, organic wine production is an increasing
466 trend in Madrid wine-growing region. The use of some products such as sulphur dioxide
467 (SO₂) is limited for its elaboration, so the yeast selection to reduce the occurrence notes
468 linked to the limitation of levels of SO₂ allowed to organic elaboration has been an
469 objective in our investigations. In a work of Balboa-Lagunero et al. (Balboa-Lagunero et
470 al., 2013) with five autochthonous *S. cerevisiae* from D.O. “Vinos de Madrid”, the
471 relationship between pro-oxidative amino acids (Phe, Met, Leu) content and the final
472 amount of aldehydes fraction regarding oxidation notes in organic wines was studied.
473 Thus, *S. cerevisiae* CLI 271 was selected on the basis of its high consumption of amino
474 acids precursors of oxidation notes and its low scores for sensorial oxidation notes. Due
475 to the effect of climate change in the current viticulture, other yeast selection criteria are
476 the adaptation to stresses inherent to wine fermentation in warm areas, such as central
477 Spain. *S. cerevisiae* G 520 from the organic cellar of Arganda subzone was selected as
478 one of the *S. cerevisiae* tolerant strains based on their performance under osmotic
479 pressure, ethanol and pH stresses (García et al., 2016) and recently, has been selected by
480 its ability for beer fermentation with special impact in final melatonin and ester (fruity
481 character) contents (Postigo et al., 2021)).

482 On the other hand, the use of non-*Saccharomyces* yeasts in wine elaboration has changed
483 the standardized way to wine production, improving the quality of the final product.
484 Several studies have been done to establish protocols for wine elaboration using different
485 co-cultures with *S. cerevisiae* and six different non-*Saccharomyces* (*T. delbrueckii* CLI
486 918, *S. pombe* CLI 1085 and CLI 1079, *C. stellata* CLI 920, *M. pulcherrima* CLI 457, *L.*
487 *thermotolerans* 9-6C) (Table 1), all from D.O. “Vinos de Madrid” (García, Apolinar-
488 Valiente, et al., 2017; García, Arroyo, et al., 2017; García, Esteve-Zarzoso, et al., 2017).
489 In general, sequential inoculations were highlighted by their contribution to higher
490 complexity and quality in final wines (García, Arroyo, et al., 2017). After studying the
491 dynamics of inoculated populations by qPCR (García, Esteve-Zarzoso, et al., 2017), the
492 non-*Saccharomyces* strains were present throughout the fermentation process, although
493 *S. cerevisiae* strain was the most abundant at the end of the fermentation. As well, non-
494 *Saccharomyces* yeast adapted to fermentation stresses in their winegrowing area is a
495 favourable feature for selection. A recent study (García et al., 2021) has allowed to choice
496 of native non-*Saccharomyces* strains resistant to osmotic pressure, ethanol and pH,
497 showing *L. fermentati* CLI 1220, *L. thermotolerans* CLI 1219 and *S. pombe* CLI 1085
498 strains (Table 1) the best adaptation of three stress conditions examined. And finally, the
499 use of non-*Saccharomyces* can also help to mitigate the effects of climate change in the
500 organoleptic characteristics of wines. One effect is the high ethanol content due to the

501 increased concentration of grape sugars in warm climate areas. Four non-*Saccharomyces*
502 strains (Table 1) (*W. anomalus* 21A-5C, *M. guilliermondii* CLI 1217 and *M. pulcherrima*
503 CLI 68 and CLI 460) in sequential culture with *S. cerevisiae* were able to reduce the
504 ethanol content (0.8-1.3%, v/v), producing wines with high glycerol and fruity and sweet
505 character (García et al., 2021).

506

507 **Yeast selection in Castilla La Mancha**

508

509 The Region of Castilla-La Mancha (CLM), with an ancient and great winemaking
510 tradition, represents approximately half of the cultivated vineyard area in Spain and the
511 largest vineyard cultivation area in the world. From the University of Castilla La Mancha
512 numerous studies have been carried out related to wine yeasts, focusing on both
513 *Saccharomyces* and non-*Saccharomyces* yeasts.

514 The first investigations of the group were carried out in several wineries situated in the
515 viticultural area of Valdepeñas (Briones et al., 1995), where dry yeasts were never been
516 utilized. During two successive years, samples from three different cellars were taken at
517 different fermentation stages. A total of 392 isolates were obtained, resulting in 174
518 strains by karyotype analysis using CHEF technique. Then a selection process was
519 performed, in which different criteria were used: good fermentation rate, capacity for
520 completely consuming reducing sugars, resistance towards ethanol, SO₂ and high sugar
521 concentration, inability to produce SH₂ or any other off-flavours, and killer or neutral
522 phenotype. Finally, vinifications were carried on using 20 strains that possessed the above
523 characteristics in order to select those with better organoleptic properties. Nine strains
524 were selected to be used as starter culture. SafEno™ UCLM S325 and UCLM S377 are
525 currently commercialized by Fermentis-Division of S.I.Lesaffre (Table 1).

526 Subsequently, other yeast selection processes have been carried out and are currently used
527 as starter cultures for the production of their wines. An example of this is the selection in
528 the ecological surroundings of Guijoso Appellation of Origin (A.O) (Fernández-González
529 & Briones, 2013). From a total of 370 *Saccharomyces* isolated yeasts, 23 different
530 molecular patterns were obtained by DNA mitochondrial restriction. After that, a
531 selection process was performed, and some traits were assayed, such as rate of
532 fermentation at 25 and 15 °C, inability to produce SH₂, foam production or acetic acid,
533 capacity to consume sugars, killer phenotype, no flocculation capacity and low phenolic
534 off-flavour (POF) production. Then, natural musts from Chardonnay and Cabernet
535 Sauvignon varieties were fermented using preselected strains and the wines obtained were
536 analyzed and tasted. Two strains (G01 and G04) were selected and nowadays are used as
537 starters in Sanchez Muliterno winery (Table 1).

538 Regarding non-*Saccharomyces* yeasts, several studies have been carried out in various
539 cellars in the Region. Fernandez et al. (Fernández et al., 1999) sampled musts and wines
540 from three wineries situated in La Mancha Appellation of Origin (A.O), obtaining from
541 47 out of 480 isolates belonging to non-*Saccharomyces* yeasts. Results revealed the
542 presence of nine species, most (38%) identified as *Hanseniaspora uvarum*, followed by
543 *Lachancea thermotolerans* and *Debaryomyces hansenii*, each about 17% of the total
544 isolates. In other work (Fernández et al., 2000), enzymatic activities of potential interest
545 in wine-making, such as proteolytic, polygalacturonase, and beta-glucosidase, were
546 studied in 182 non-*Saccharomyces* yeasts isolated from musts before and at the onset of
547 fermentation at five wine cellars operating under the La Mancha A.O. Nearly 80% of the
548 wild yeasts possessed one or more enzymes of biotechnological interest and was strain-
549 dependent. A total of 78 non-*Saccharomyces* were identified by using biochemical probes

550 and molecular ITS-RFLP analysis, and 12 different species were obtained.
551 *Metschnikowia pulcherrima* was the majority profile (41%), followed by *Pichia*
552 *Kudriavzevii* (28.2%) (previously identified as *Brettanomyces clausenii*). In addition,
553 other species were isolated in a minority way, such as *Debaryomyces hansenii*, *Pichia*
554 *membranifaciens*, *Pichia krusei*, *Candida stellata* and *Kluyveromyces thermotolerans*.
555 Beta-Glucosidase activity contributes to aroma formation during the winemaking process.
556 Fernández-González et al. (Fernández-González et al., 2003) verify whether several
557 strains of wine yeasts belonging to different species such as *Metschnikowia pulcherrima*,
558 *Debaryomyces hansenii*, *Kluyveromyces thermotolerans*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*,
559 *Hanseniaspora uvarum* and *Pichia kluyveri* were able to hydrolyse glycoconjugated
560 forms of the terpenoids, norisoprenoids and benzenoids occurring in Muscat must and
561 transform the produced aglycons. The results obtained confirmed the role played by
562 yeasts in releasing volatile compounds from non-volatile precursors. Among studied wine
563 yeasts, *Hanseniaspora uvarum* (Table 1) was the one that released a greater range of
564 volatile compounds analyzed by CG-MS. The comparison of data obtained for the Muscat
565 natural glycosides and the synthetic glucoside p-NPG (4-nitrophenyl-h-D-
566 glucopyranoside), showed that most yeast species might hydrolyse pNPG, but are not able
567 to hydrolyze the muscat glucosides. Some mixed inoculation with different yeasts strains
568 were carried out in our Region. Barrajon et al. (Barrajon et al., 2011) studied the potential
569 benefit to use co-inoculation of eight wild strains (seven *S. cerevisiae* and one
570 *Torulaspora delbrueckii* (W37) previously isolated by Barrajon et al., (Barrajon et al.,
571 2009) with two commercial *S. cerevisiae*. A total of 8 co-cultures were carried out, each
572 containing two wild strains and 1 of the commercial *S. cerevisiae* strains. Despite the fact
573 that only one strain dominated at the end of the process, co-cultures wines released
574 different concentrations of major volatile compounds than single strains, especially
575 higher alcohols and acetaldehydes. So, this study demonstrates that the final wine
576 composition may be modulated and enhanced by using suitable combinations of yeast
577 strains. The use of mixed inoculation of non-*Saccharomyces* yeasts and *S. cerevisiae* in
578 wine fermentations is of increasing interest for quality enhancement and improved
579 complexity of wines. Izquierdo et al. (Izquierdo Cañas et al., 2014) studied the effect of
580 sequential inoculation of *Wickerhamomyces anomalus* previously selected in Castilla La
581 Mancha region with interesting enological properties in terms of secondary metabolite
582 production (Izquierdo Cañas et al., 2011) and a commercial *S. cerevisiae* strain. The red
583 wines elaborated with mixed fermentations were preferred by 71.5 % of the tasters and
584 were particularly appreciated for their floral and/or fruity notes.

585

586 **Yeast selection in eastern Spain**

587

588 The first documented study of yeast diversity on winemaking in eastern Spain was
589 performed by Somavilla et al. (Somavilla et al., 1971). This study included data of
590 fermentation performed at some wineries placed at the Denomination of Origin (D.O.)
591 Utiel-Requena. Later, Khayyat et al. (Khayyat et al., 1982) and, mainly, Mateos et al.
592 (Mateos et al., 1985) described the diversity of the yeast microbiota in this D.O. Our
593 group began to study the yeast appearing along with fermentation of Bobal, Cabernet-
594 Sauvignon, Garnacha, Tempranillo and Macabeo grape musts in two cellars, two vintages
595 (1982 and 1983) and two fermentation methods (traditional and Bidone). We recorded
596 non-*Saccharomyces* species that were present in different frequencies in the sampled
597 grape musts: *Kloeckera apis* 100%, *Candida stellata* 87%, the yeast-like fungus
598 *Aureobasidium pullulans* 80%, *Pichia kluyveri* and *Candida pulcherrima* 53%, *Pichia*

599 *fermentans* 47%, *Hansenula anomala* 20%, *Candida boidinii*, *Pichia membranaefaciens*,
600 *Rhodotorula rubra*, and *Torulaspora delbrueckii* 13%, and *Hansenula mrakii*, *Kloeckera*
601 *japonica* and *Sporobolomyces roseus* 7%. Different races of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*
602 were found in some of the fermenting grape musts but not in all; the most frequently
603 found was *S. cerevisiae* race *cerevisiae* 40% and was isolated from Bobal and
604 Tempranillo. The races *S. cerevisiae* race *bayanus*, *S. cerevisiae* race *capensis*, *S.*
605 *cerevisiae* race *chevalieri* and *S. cerevisiae* race *uvarum* were sporadically isolated in
606 some musts of Bobal, with a frequency of 7% (Pardo, 1987; Pardo et al., 1989).
607 Later, in 2008-2011, an extensive search was carried out to isolate and select *S. cerevisiae*
608 yeasts from organic vineyards and wines. This project aimed to select organic yeasts with
609 suitable characteristics for fermenting musts of the Bobal, Cabernet-Sauvignon and
610 Tempranillo varieties from the Utiel-Requena DO. The general criteria used for their
611 selection were moderate ethanol production, organic acid production, no production of
612 urea and H₂S, rapid depletion of sugars, β -glucosidase activity if possible, flocculant
613 capacity, ability to grow at high osmotic pressures, ability to resist high concentrations of
614 ethanol and SO₂, and improvement of the organoleptic profile of wines. From 132
615 isolates, 64 were identified as *S. cerevisiae* by analysis of the ITS region of their
616 ribosomal operons. Among these isolates, 24 distinct strains were identified based on
617 restriction pattern analysis of mitochondrial DNA (Supplementary Figure 1). Based on
618 the selection criteria, strains 55A, 110AP and 80A, isolated from Tempranillo, Cabernet-
619 Sauvignon and Bobal, respectively, were chosen. The strain that showed the best
620 implantation capacity in real winemaking conditions in the three types of grape must
621 carried out in volumes of 50 L, was 55A and was, therefore, the chosen strain to perform
622 a semi-industrial scale (1500 L) trial. The wines obtained showed lower alcohol
623 concentration, higher total acidity, and lower residual sugar concentration than those
624 fermented with the controls (Lucio et al., 2009; Polo et al., 2013, 2011).
625 During 2015 and 2016, the ENOLAB group characterised *S. cerevisiae* and non-
626 *Saccharomyces* yeasts in grape musts of Merlot, Garnacha and Cabernet-Sauvignon
627 varieties from Pago Chozas-Carrascal wines produced at this winery located in San
628 Antonio de Requena, Valencia, Spain. Ninety-five isolates were obtained and identified
629 as *S. cerevisiae* by analysis of their ribosomal ITS regions. After analysing the mtDNA
630 restriction patterns, 24 distinct isolates were obtained and considered different strains. Of
631 the 24 strains, only two appeared in all three types of grape musts, 6 in two of them, and
632 the rest were unique to each fermentation, indicating a high diversity of strains in a single
633 winery. The characterisation and selection of strains were based on the following criteria:
634 growth kinetics, glucose and fructose depletion, ethanol, acetic acid and glycerol
635 production, resistance to increasing osmotic pressures, dependence on exogenous N
636 nutrition. The novelty of this characterisation is that all experiments were carried out on
637 the same must from which the yeasts were isolated, making the extrapolation of the results
638 much more feasible than if a synthetic must had been used. Based on the above criteria,
639 strains 22H, 32C and 32F were selected (Ut et al., 2021).
640 Regarding the isolation of non-*Saccharomyces* in Bobal, Cabernet-Sauvignon, Garnacha
641 and Merlot grape musts from Pago Chozas Carrascal, a total of 88 isolates were obtained:
642 5 isolates from the Bobal musts, 35 isolates from the musts of the Cabernet-Sauvignon
643 variety, 14 isolates from the musts of Garnacha, and 34 isolates from the musts of the
644 Merlot variety. The isolates were identified by sequencing the ITS ribosomal fragment.
645 Molecular characterisation of these isolates by amplification of microsatellite regions

646 with primers (GTG)₅, M13 and (GACA)₄ resulted in the appearance of 22 different
647 profiles (Table 1), of which 11 belonged to *Hanseniaspora uvarum* (P1-P4, P6, P10-11,
648 P13-14, P18 and P22); 1 to *Torula delbrueckii* (P5); 1 to *Lachancea thermotolerans* (P7);
649 2 to *Hanseniaspora opuntiae/guilliermondii* (P8 and P16); 1 to *Hanseniaspora*
650 *opuntiae/uvarum* (P9); 1 to *Metschnikowia pulcherrima* (P12); 2 to *Hanseniaspora*
651 *guilliermondii*; 2 to *Starmerella bacillaris* (P17 and P19); and 1 to *Hanseniaspora*
652 *valbyensis* (P21). The greatest diversity of strains is observed in the species *H. uvarum*,
653 which appears in all the grape musts analysed, particularly the strain with the P1 profile.
654 Some species have only been isolated in one of the three varieties, such as *T. delbrueckii*,
655 *H. valbyensis*, *L. thermotolerans* and *M. pulcherrima*, found in Cabernet-Sauvignon, and
656 *S. bacillaris* in Bobal (Le Coz, 2017; Polo et al., 2018). Among the criteria chosen when
657 selecting non-*Saccharomyces* for inoculation with *S. cerevisiae*, one of the most
658 important is their resistance to sulphur dioxide, as many of these species are sensitive to
659 it. Another very important criterion, from a food safety point of view, is that they were
660 unable to produce biogenic amines. Based on these criteria, two isolates of *H. uvarum*
661 belonging to profile P1 (42D and 49C) and one isolate of *T. delbrueckii* belonging to T4
662 (58E) were selected. In addition to these, other criteria were taken into account, such as
663 the ability to survive or grow after subsequent inoculation with *S. cerevisiae* (22H) and
664 the degree of implantation in the fermentation of Cabernet-Sauvignon, Garnacha and
665 Merlot grape musts. It was observed that the implantation percentages of non-
666 *Saccharomyces* depended in part on time elapsed between the inoculation of the non-
667 *Saccharomyces* yeast and the *S. cerevisiae* yeast, with the longer the time elapsed, the
668 higher the implantation percentages. The highest implantation percentages between the
669 non-*Saccharomyces* tested were achieved with *Torulaspora delbrueckii* 58E, regardless
670 of the time between the two inoculations: more than 95% before the *S. cerevisiae*
671 inoculation. The implantation was much higher on Garnacha and Cabernet-Sauvignon
672 than on Merlot wines. The sequential inoculation of the *T. delbrueckii* 58E and *S.*
673 *cerevisiae* 22H strains gives the wines more intense sweetness and reduces the
674 astringency in the Cabernet-Sauvignon, Garnacha and Merlot wines tested (Morillas
675 Álvarez, 2020).

676

677 **Selection of film yeasts in Sherry region**

678

679 Sherry wines are produced in the Jerez area of southern Spain, and legally protected by
680 “Jerez-Xères-Sherry” and “Manzanilla-Sanlúcar de Barrameda” Appellation of Origin.
681 They are one of the most distinctive and valuable Spanish wines. Among them, Fino and
682 Manzanilla stand out because of a particular and dynamic ageing system, called “criaderas
683 and soleras”. The first phase of this process is called “sobretablas”, which consists of a
684 young wine of the grape variety *Vitis vinifera* L. var. Palomino Fino fortified with wine
685 ethanol to 15-15.5% (v/v). The intermediate stages are called “criaderas”, while the last
686 row (*solera*) is the only one that contains the finished wine, being the sole which can be
687 extracted (maximum 1/6 of the volume) and commercialized. The amount of wine
688 removed from the *solera* is replaced with the same volume of wine from the next row
689 (first *criadera*), which in turn is filled with wine from the next higher scale (second
690 *criadera*) and so on until the largest scale (Cordero-Bueso et al., 2018). The process of
691 removing wine from one scale and refilling from the next is called “saca and rocío”, which
692 is a decisive step since it provides aeration as well as nutrient exchange between the
693 different aged wines, promoting the maintenance of the veil of flor during the entire

694 ageing process (Berlanga et al., 2004). During biological ageing, a biofilm is developed
695 on the wine surface called “veil of flor”, which consists mostly of yeasts belonging to the
696 *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* species (Martínez et al., 1995). Since the medium is deficient
697 in both sugars and nitrogen sources, flor yeasts are capable of aerobically assimilating
698 different metabolites of the wine, thus promoting the formation of different ones which
699 are distinctive of this particular type of wine, such as acetaldehyde, higher alcohols or
700 acetoin (Moreno-García et al., 2015; Pozo-Bayón & Moreno-Arribas, 2011). Flor yeasts
701 have traditionally been classified based on their physiological features into four races
702 within the species *S. cerevisiae*: *beticus*, *cheresiensis*, *montuliensis* and *rouxii* (Martínez
703 et al., 1995). However, according to the latest yeast taxonomy, this classification is
704 currently obsolete (Kurtzman et al., 1998) based on the inability to differentiate between
705 them using molecular techniques (Esteve-Zarzoso et al., 2004; Ruíz-Muñoz et al., 2017).
706 Moreover, some studies have reported significant differences in the composition of wines
707 obtained by different strains that formerly belonged to the same race (Marin-Menguiano
708 et al., 2017; Rodríguez et al., 2013). Flor yeasts are adapted to very stressful conditions
709 (i.e. main carbon and nitrogen sources depleted, high alcohol content, presence of heavy
710 metals, environmental factors). This is consistent with what other authors have already
711 described in genomic studies with flor yeasts from different regions of Europe, in which
712 it is demonstrated that flor yeasts have a common phylogenetic origin and high
713 specialization (Coi et al., 2017; Eldarov et al., 2018; Legras et al., 2014). In this sense,
714 flor yeasts form very tight clusters close to the main wine clade. As mentioned above, *flor*
715 yeasts have traditionally been characterised according to their ability to ferment a few
716 carbon sources, specifically galactose, maltose, raffinose and sucrose (Martínez et al.,
717 1995). In this sense, several studies have focused on characterising the yeasts present in
718 different wineries in the region during biological ageing.

719 Thus, the predominance of one of the formerly races has been reported since the first
720 studies carried out in this region (Martínez et al., 1997). Different ageing scales from
721 different wineries of the same company were analysed. Results showed that, although
722 there were no differences between the wineries overall, there were differences between
723 the scales when considered individually, together with a succession of some races of flor
724 yeasts during biological ageing. However, other similar studies (Esteve-Zarzoso et al.,
725 2001; Ibeas et al., 1997; Mesa et al., 1999) did not observe such ecological progression,
726 but the dominance of one flor yeast was found homogeneously at all ageing scales.
727 Furthermore, by applying molecular techniques such as mitochondrial DNA restriction
728 analysis or chromosomal profiles (Esteve-Zarzoso et al., 2004; Mesa et al., 1999) and
729 analysing other physiological properties, such as ethanol, acetaldehyde stress or velum-
730 forming rate (Aranda et al., 2002), no correlation with the formerly races was established.
731 Currently, the biodiversity of three wineries in the region belonging to the same company
732 was analysed, obtaining nine different profiles using microsatellite and interdelta
733 typification (Ruiz-Muñoz et al., 2020). These could be classified into the former races
734 *beticus* being the predominant one as have been already described, followed by the
735 *cheresiensis* race. It is consistent with what had already been described in some of the
736 earlier studies (Mesa et al., 1999). These nine genotypes could also be differentiated
737 according to their physiological properties. Thus, some of them showed some features
738 such as the ability to assimilate melibiose, inulin or urea. In this case, a relative fluctuation
739 between *S. cerevisiae* genotypes was also found, being seasonal-dependent (Ruiz-Muñoz
740 et al., 2020). It is also remarkable that four other species (*W. anomalus*, *P.*
741 *membranaefaciens*, *P. manshurica*, and *P. kudriavzevii*) were found in this study (Table
742 1). Although they were promptly isolated in some of the analysed barrels, and their origin
743 remains unclear, they have been of great interest since these strains must be adapted to

744 the specific and stressful environment of the Sherry wines in an active growth rate. It is
745 supported by their ability to form biofilm and show some different phenotypic features
746 related to their species (unpublished), as already mentioned elsewhere (Mesa et al., 1999).
747 In addition, 15 flor strains isolated from six different wineries in the Jerez region (Table
748 1) were used to carry out biological ageing in pure culture at a laboratory scale (Morales
749 et al., 2020). Significant differences were found, although four main groups of flor yeasts
750 with a high correlation could be established by principal component analysis. Two strains
751 showed interesting features to be used as potential starters. Considering these studies, it
752 can be inferred that the overall diversity in biological ageing for Sherry production is very
753 low, as the system exerts itself pressure and selection. However, the fluctuation between
754 flor strains is complex, and its behaviour cannot be generalised as it is particular to each
755 winery. Although flor yeasts are not commercially available to be used as starters, they
756 should be considered as very useful not only for producing Sherry wine but also for many
757 other applications due to their metabolic and genetic peculiarities.

758

759 ***Lachancea thermotolerans*: successful isolations from Ribera de Duero, La** 760 **Mancha and Uclés regions**

761

762 *Lachancea thermotolerans* (formerly *Kluyveromyces thermotolerans*) is a trendy species
763 for its use in wine acidification to improve microbiological stability, sensory profile and
764 freshness (Hranilovic et al., 2018; Morata et al., 2018; Porter et al., 2019). The main
765 feature of *L. thermotolerans* is the transformation of sugars into lactic acid, which
766 provides a powerful bio-tool to control pH in flat wines from warm areas (Banilas et al.,
767 2016; Comitini et al., 2011; Gobbi et al., 2013; Hranilovic et al., 2021; Morata et al.,
768 2019; Vaquero et al., 2020), and thus providing a suitable natural replacement for
769 chemical acidification (Vaquero, Izquierdo-Cañas, et al., 2021). Furthermore, it is
770 possible to reduce the total sulphite content at low pH due to the high amount of molecular
771 and free SO₂ (Morata, Loira, et al., 2021). Additionally, *L. thermotolerans* has other
772 interesting properties such as low volatile acidity production (Vilela, 2018), desired
773 enzymatic activities and influence on aroma profile (Morata et al., 2018; Porter et al.,
774 2019), and lower production of medium-chain fatty acids (Hranilovic et al., 2021). In
775 Spain, selection processes have been developed to obtain *L. thermotolerans* strains in
776 most regions, focusing mainly on acidification because the warm conditions produce
777 grapes with high sugar content and high pH that can be technically and sensorially
778 improved by using selected *L. thermotolerans* biotypes. After selection, some of these
779 strains have been evaluated at industrial level and tested to be produced as commercial
780 dry yeasts (Figure 2). The strains were selected from Ribera de Duero, La Mancha and
781 Uclés regions (Table 1). The characterization included acidification and production of
782 fermentative volatiles during sequential fermentations with *Saccharomyces* in musts from
783 different grape varieties at several temperatures and variable SO₂ content (Morata et al.,
784 2019; Vaquero et al., 2020; Vaquero, Izquierdo-Cañas, et al., 2021). The acidification
785 produced a pH reduction that can range from 0.1-0.5 units depending on grape
786 composition, fermentation temperature, SO₂ content and degree of implantation. The
787 trials were performed at small laboratory scale (8-1000 mL) and also at pilot (500-1,000
788 L) and industrial scale in wineries (8,000-12,000 L) using suitable controls with *S.*
789 *cerevisiae* and commercial strains of Lt (Laktia™, Concerto™) (Figure 3). Moreover,
790 biocompatibility, fermentative behaviour and acidification were studied in mixed-use

791 with other non-*Saccharomyces* such as *Hanseniaspora vineae*, *Torulaspora delbrueckii*
792 and *Metschnikowia pulcherrima* (Vaquero, Loira, et al., 2021).

793

794 ***Schizosaccharomyces pombe*: applications from Spain to Portugal**

795

796 This fission yeast shows interesting applications in wine biotechnology (Loira et al.,
797 2018; Suárez-Lepe et al., 2012), including demalication producing malo-alcoholic
798 fermentation (Gallander, 1977; Rankine, 1966), colour protection through the production
799 of stable pyranoanthocyanins (Loira et al., 2015; Morata et al., 2012), the high release of
800 cell wall polysaccharides during ageing on lees (Domizio et al., 2017; Palomero et al.,
801 2009; Romani et al., 2018), urease activity to decrease ethyl carbamate precursors
802 (Lubbers et al., 1996), biogenic amines control (De Fatima et al., 2007), and gluconic acid
803 reduction (Peinado et al., 2004). Moreover, many strains have high fermentative power
804 (13-15% v/v), allowing for single fermentations without the sequential use of *S.*
805 *cerevisiae* (Loira et al., 2018; Suárez-Lepe et al., 2012). Concerning colour, the formation
806 of 11 mg/L of vitisin A has been observed during fermentation with *S. pombe* strain 938
807 (Morata et al., 2012), with a range of total pyranoanthocyanins of 12-19 mg/L depending
808 on the strain used. A high release of Pyruvic acid by *S. pombe* favours the condensation
809 with malvidin-3-o-glucoside to form Vitisin A. The selection works started in 1957 with
810 several strains from Cordoba's musts and concentrated juices. Strains 936, 938, 939 and
811 2139 from the former IFI-CSIC collection are currently included in the CECT collection
812 (Spanish Type Culture Collection located at the University of Valencia,
813 [https://www.uv.es/uvweb/coleccion-espanola-cultivos-tipo/es/coleccion-espanola-](https://www.uv.es/uvweb/coleccion-espanola-cultivos-tipo/es/coleccion-espanola-cultivos-tipo-1285872233521.html)
814 [cultivos-tipo-1285872233521.html](https://www.uv.es/uvweb/coleccion-espanola-cultivos-tipo/es/coleccion-espanola-cultivos-tipo-1285872233521.html)). These strains have been used in some of the
815 applications described before on the improvement of sensory or technical properties of
816 wines (Loira et al., 2015; Morata et al., 2012). Additionally, biomass from a selected *S.*
817 *pombe* strain is produced in Portugal (Proenol, Promalic™, <https://www.proenol.com>)
818 (Table 1) as reticulated dry yeast in alginate beads for selective wine demalication during
819 fermentation to replace malolactic fermentation (Portugal et al., 2011), and to control the
820 production of biogenic amines (De Fatima et al., 2007).

821

822 ***Hanseniaspora* spp.: selections started in Valencia and spread in the whole of Spain**

823

824 The early selections of *Hanseniaspora* spp started in Spain with the work of Paloma
825 Manzanares and coworkers (Rojas et al., 2001, 2003; Viana et al., 2008, 2011). They
826 focused a lot on the production of acetate esters, mainly considering fruity and floral
827 esters such as isoamyl acetate (banana aroma, sensory threshold of 0.03 mg/L, (Ferreira
828 et al., 2000)) and 2-phenyl ethyl acetate (rose aroma, sensory threshold 0.25 mg/L,
829 (Ferreira et al., 2000)). They studied eight strains of the species *Hanseniaspora*
830 *guilliermondii*, *H. uvarum*, *H. osmophila* and *H. vineae*, however, most of the strains were
831 taken from the CECT, and only 2 of them were selected in Spain and Portugal (Viana et
832 al., 2008, 2011). Recently, within the Freshwines project led by Lallemand, several
833 *Hanseniaspora* strains have been isolated in La Mancha and Jerez wine regions, of which
834 14 belong to the species *H. uvarum*, *H. opuntiae*, and *H. guilliermondii*, have been
835 selected. Among them, strain A56 (*H. opuntiae*) (Table 1) selected in La Mancha has
836 been used at the laboratory- (8 mL & 1 L), pilot- (30 L) and industrial-scale (12,000 L).
837 This strain has shown a complex aroma with fruity and floral nuances enhanced when

838 used on flat varieties such as Airen (*Vitis vinifera* L.) but can also increase body and
839 palatability (Morata, Loira, et al., 2021). Furthermore, low compatibility of *H. vineae*
840 with *L. thermotolerans* has been observed (Vaquero, Loira, et al., 2021), but quite good
841 with *H. opuntiae* (Morata, Escott, et al., 2021). The impact of using *L. thermotolerans*
842 and *H. opuntiae* on flat varieties of warm areas is the simultaneous improvement of
843 acidity together with the formation of aroma compounds and improvement of structure
844 (Morata, Escott, et al., 2021).

845

846

847 **Conclusions**

848 Wine yeast selection provides a powerful tool to improve wine quality, as it allows the
849 use of suitable pure inoculum or yeast mixed cultures that can be applied in co-inoculation
850 or sequential inoculations to enhance sensory, safety and technical parameters, enhancing
851 sustainability and contributing to the design of new oenological production facing to
852 global changes, not only during fermentation but also in pre-fermentative applications
853 and biological ageing. Moreover, increasing evidence suggests an intriguing role of wine
854 microbes to improve the unique traits of regional wine, sustaining the production of high-
855 quality products associated with the numerous Geographical Indications in the sector. In
856 this light, the present review compiles comprehensive information on several decades of
857 wine yeast research in the Iberia Peninsula to provide traditional and new ways of
858 managing biotechnological processes in the wine industry.

859

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Table 1. Yeast strains selected in several regions of the Iberian Peninsula and their main characteristics. Includes *Saccharomyces*, film yeasts for biological ageing and non-*Saccharomyces*.

Specie	year	Number of strains	Region	Substrate of isolation	Features	Identification	Sensory impact	Strain/Commercial product/brand	Reference
<i>Candida cantarelli</i>	2001	n.d.	Jerez-Xèrés-Sherry (Jerez)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance	RFLP-mtDNA PCR ITS1-ITS2	n.d	González-Byass	(Esteve-Zarzoso et al., 2001)
<i>Candida pulcherrima</i>	1982-83	8	Utiel-Requena	Bobal, Macabeo, Garnacha, Tempranillo & Cabernet-Sauvignon grape musts		Phenotypical tests		EI-10, FI-8, BI-8, NIII-1, Maci-2, GarI-1, TempI-2, CSI-1	(Pardo, 1987)
<i>Candida stellata</i>	2006	1	Madrid	Wine	Glycerol producer; pectinase activity; esters and β -phenylethyl alcohol production	Selective media: LYS/WL, PCR-RFLP of 5.8S ITS region, sequencing of D1/D2 region of the 26S rDNA gen	Fruity (green apple and grapefruit) and floral aroma; sweet character, freshness and full-bodied on the palate	CLI 920	(Cordero-Bueso et al., 2013; García et al., 2018; García, Arroyo, et al., 2017; García, Esteve-Zarzoso, et al., 2017)
<i>Candida stellata</i>	1983	1	Utiel-Requena	Fermenting Bobal grape must		Phenotypical tests		BoII-2	(Pardo, 1987)

<i>Dekkera bruxellensis</i>	2001	n.d.	Jerez-Xères-Sherry (Jerez)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance	RFLP-mtDNA PCR ITS1-ITS2	n.d	González-Byass	(Esteve-Zarzoso et al., 2001)
<i>Hanseniaspora opuntiae</i>	2018	1	La Mancha	Grape	7% 2-phenylethyl acetate	Lysine, chromagar and PCR (sequences of ITS-5.8S)	Floral aroma and palatability	A56 under industrial evaluation by Lallemand	(Morata, Escott, et al., 2021)
<i>Hanseniaspora uvarum</i>	2003	31	La Mancha	Must	-	PCR ITS1-ITS2	Hydrolyze muscat terpenes	-	(Fernández-González et al., 2003)
<i>Kloeckera apis</i>	1983	1	Utiel-Requena	Fermenting Garnacha grape must		Phenotypical tests		GI-10	(Pardo, 1987)
<i>Kloeckera japonica</i>	1983	1	Utiel-Requena	Fermenting Macabeo grape must		Phenotypical tests		MacI-3	(Pardo, 1987)
<i>Lachancea fermentati</i>	2007	1	Madrid	Must fermentation	Resistant to osmotic pressure, pH and ethanol; acetate esters production	Selective media: LYS/WL, PCR-RFLP of 5.8S ITS region, sequencing of D1/D2 region of the 26S rDNA gene	Banana and fruity flavors	CLI 1220	(Cordero-Bueso et al., 2013; García et al., 2021)
<i>Lachancea thermotolerans</i>	2008	1 (/135)	Douro - Portugal	Refermentation on process of acidic wine by fresh crushed grapes/must	Acetic acid reduction without complete sugar consumption in 48h	Amplification of the D1-D2 variable domain at the 5' end of the 26S rDNA with primers NL-1 and NL-4 and sequencing of the amplified fragments	Lower acidity perception in mouth and in-nose	44C Not commercialized	(Vilela-Moura et al., 2008; Vilela et al., 2015)
<i>Lachancea thermotolerans</i>	2015	1	Ribera del Duero	Grape	9% vol lactic acid 3-9	Lysine, chromagar and PCR (sequences of ITS-5.8S)	Neutral aroma medium-high fresh acidity	L31 under industrial	(Morata et al., 2019; Vaquero et

								evaluation by Lallemand	al., 2020; Vaquero, Izquierdo- Cañas, et al., 2021; Vaquero, Loira, et al., 2021)
<i>Lachancea thermotoleran s</i>	2018	1	La Mancha	Grape	9% vol lactic acid 2-8	Lysine, chromagar and PCR (sequences of ITS-5.8S)	Neutral aroma medium-high fresh acidity	A54 under industrial evaluation by Lallemand	(Vaquero et al., 2020)
<i>Lachancea thermotoleran s</i>	2018	2	Uclés	Grape	9% vol lactic acid 0.5-2	Lysine, chromagar and PCR (sequences of ITS-5.8S)	Neutral aroma low fresh acidity	F108 & F111	(Vaquero et al., 2020)
<i>Lachancea thermotoleran s</i>		1	Galicia	Grape must	Increase acidity Lactic acid production Alcohol reduction	Selective media: WL/Lysine Agar Molecular: RFLPs of ITS1 and ITS2 of 5.8S rRNA gene; Sequencing of D1/D2 region of 26S rDNA	acidity	Lt93	(Blanco et al., 2020; Blanco, Castrillo, et al., 2021)
<i>Lachancea thermotoleran s</i>	2006	1	Madrid	Must fermentation	High lactic acid production in pure and sequential culture; resistant to osmotic pressure, pH and ethanol	Selective media: LYS/WL, PCR-RFLP of 5.8S ITS region, sequencing of D1/D2 region of the 26S rDNA gene	Acidity, high aroma intensity, ripe fruit (pear) and floral aroma notes	9-6C	(García et al., 2016; García, Arroyo, et al., 2017; García, Esteve- Zarzoso, et al., 2017)
<i>Lachancea thermotoleran s</i>	2007	1	Madrid	Must fermentation	Resistant to osmotic pressure, pH	Selective media: LYS/WL,	n.d.	CLI 1219	(Cordero- Bueso et al., 2013;

					and ethanol; high β -glucosidase activity	PCR-RFLP of 5.8S ITS region, sequencing of D1/D2 region of the 26S rDNA gen			García et al., 2021)
<i>Lachancea thermotolerans</i>	1982	1	Utiel-Requena	Fermenting Bobal grape must		Phenotypical tests		BoII-3	(Pardo, 1987)
<i>Metschnikowia fruticola</i>		1	Galicia	Grape must	Increase of esters, acetates and C6-C10 volatile acids	Selective media: WL/Lysine Agar Molecular: RFLPs of ITS1 and ITS2 of 5.8S rRNA gene; Sequencing of D1/D2 region of 26S rDNA	Fruity	Mf278	(Blanco, Castrillo, et al., 2021; Castrillo et al., 2019)
<i>Metschnikowia pulcherrima</i>	1995	1	Madrid	Must fermentation	High glycerol production; High β -glucosidase activity	Selective media: LYS/WL, PCR-RFLP of 5.8S ITS region, sequencing of D1/D2 region of the 26S rDNA gene	Ripe fruit and banana aroma	CLI 457	(Arroyo et al., 2010; García, Arroyo, et al., 2017; García, Esteve-Zarzoso, et al., 2017)
<i>Metschnikowia pulcherrima</i>	1995	1	Madrid	Must fermentation	Ethanol content reduction (0.8%, v/v); medium-high osmotic pressure and pH resistance, low ethanol resistance; high glycerol	Selective media: LYS/WL, PCR-RFLP of 5.8S ITS region, sequencing of D1/D2 region of the 26S rDNA gene	Fruity aroma compounds	CLI 460	(Arroyo et al., 2010; García et al., 2020, 2021)

					production (9.30 g/L); high β -glucosidase activity				
<i>Metschnikowi a pulcherrima</i>	1993	1	Madrid	Must fermentation	Ethanol content reduction (1.3%, v/v); high glycerol production (8.32 g/L); high β -glucosidase activity	Selective media: LYS/WL, PCR-RFLP of 5.8S ITS region, sequencing of D1/D2 region of the 26S rDNA gene	Fruity aroma compounds	CLI 68	(Arroyo et al., 2010; García et al., 2020)
<i>Meyerozyma guilliermondii</i>	2006	1	Madrid	Must fermentation	Ethanol content reduction (1.2%, v/v); esters and β -phenylethyl alcohol production	Selective media: LYS/WL, PCR-RFLP of 5.8S ITS region, sequencing of D1/D2 region of the 26S rDNA gene	Fruity and floral aroma compounds	CLI 1217	(García et al., 2020)
<i>Pichia fermentans</i>	1982-83	2	Utiel-Requena	Bobal & Macabeo grape must		Phenotypical tests		EI-5, MacI-4	(Pardo, 1987)
<i>Pichia kluyveri</i>		1	Galicia	Grape must	High producer of esters and C6-C10 volatile acids	Selective media: WL/Lysine Agar Molecular: RFLPs of ITS1 and ITS2 of 5.8S rRNA gene; Sequencing of D1/D2 region of 26S rDNA		Pk188	(Blanco, Castrillo, et al., 2021)
<i>Pichia kluyveri</i>	1982-83	3	Utiel-Requena	Bobal, Macabeo &		Phenotypical tests		DI-10, MacI-5, TempI-3	(Pardo, 1987)

				Tempranillo grape musts					
<i>Pichia kudriavzevii</i>	2020	NsC	Jerez-Xères-Sherry (El Puerto de Santa María)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance	RFLP-mtDNA, SSR-PCR, Interdelta elements PCR, D1/D2 PCR, Sequentiation, Fermentation and assimilation Carbon, Nitrogen and other compound tests	n.d	Bodegas Caballero S.L.	(Ruiz-Muñoz et al., 2020)
<i>Pichia manshurica</i>	2020	NsD	Jerez-Xères-Sherry (El Puerto de Santa María)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance	RFLP-mtDNA, SSR-PCR, Interdelta elements PCR, D1/D2 PCR, Sequentiation, Fermentation and assimilation Carbon, Nitrogen and other compound tests	n.d	Bodegas Caballero S.L.	(Ruiz-Muñoz et al., 2020)
<i>Pichia membranaefaciens</i>	2001	n.d.	Jerez-Xères-Sherry (Jerez)	Sobretablas Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance	RFLP-mtDNA PCR ITS1-ITS2	n.d	González-Byass	(Esteve-Zarzoso et al., 2001)
<i>Pichia membranaefaciens</i>	2020	NsA,	Jerez-Xères-Sherry (Jerez and El Puerto de Santa María)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance	RFLP-mtDNA, SSR-PCR, Interdelta elements PCR, D1/D2 PCR, Sequentiation, Fermentation and assimilation Carbon, Nitrogen and other compound tests	n.d	Bodegas Lustau S.L, Bodegas Caballero S.L.	(Ruiz-Muñoz et al., 2020)
<i>Pichia</i> ssp.	1999	n.d.	Jerez-Xères-Sherry (Jerez)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance	CHEF-PFGE mtDNA Carbon fermentation tests	n.d	Sandeman-Coprimary, S.A.	(Mesa et al., 1999)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	2008	2 (/135)	Douro - Portugal	Refermentation processes of acidic	acetic acid reduction and complete		43C & 45C		

				wines by marc from a finished wine fermentation	sugar consumption in 72h				
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	1996	3	Extremadura	Winery spontaneous fermentation	resistance to SO ₂ , killer K2 phenotype, growth at 42°C, low foam production. low volatile acidity, high ethanol production, low residual sugars	Selective media, biochemistry, gene sequencing	Fruity aroma, fresh acidity	JP73, JP85, and JP88	(Regodón et al., 1997)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	2011	2	Extremadura	Winery spontaneous fermentation	resistance to SO ₂ , killer Klus phenotype, low volatile acidity, low residual sugars	Selective media, biochemistry, gene sequencing	Increase yeast autolysis in sparkling wine	EX198, EX229	(Velázquez et al., 2016)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>		1	Galicia	Grape must	Esters and C6-C10 volatile acids producer	Selective media: WL/Lysine Agar Molecular: RFLPs-mtDNA RFLPs of ITS1 and ITS2 of 5.8S rRNA gene; Sequencing of D1/D2 region of 26S rDNA	Fruity notes, floral	XG3	(Blanco, Mirás-Avalos, Pereira, et al., 2013; Blanco, Mirás-Avalos, Suárez, et al., 2013; Blanco,

									Vázquez-Alén, et al., 2021)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	2017	FI, FII, FIII, FIV, FV, FVI, FIX, FX, MI, MII, MIII, MIV, MV, MVI and MX,	Jerez-Xères-Sherry (Jerez and Sanlúcar de Barrameda)	Fino and Manzanilla Sherry wines	15,5% etOH resistance	RFLP-mtDNA, SSR-PCR, D1/D2 PCR, Sequentiation, Fermentation and assimilation Carbon, Nitrogen and other compound tests	n.d	Sandeman-Coprimar, S.A., Barbadillo S.L., González-Byass.	(Ruíz-Muñoz et al., 2017)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	2017	A-E	Montilla-Moriles D.O. (Córdoba, Spain)	Fino of Montilla-Moriles	15,5% etOH resistance	RFLP-mtDNA, SSR-PCR Fermentation Carbon test	n.d.	Bodegas Robles, Bodegas Alvear, Cooperativa La Unión, Bodegas Perez Barquero and Bodegas Toro Albalá	(Marin-Menguiano et al., 2017)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> (Formerly <i>S. cerevisiae</i> var. <i>beticus</i>)	2020	ScA, ScF, ScH	Jerez-Xères-Sherry (Jerez and El Puerto de Santa María)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance	RFLP-mtDNA, SSR-PCR, Interdelta elements PCR, D1/D2 PCR, Sequentiation, Fermentation and assimilation Carbon, Nitrogen and other compound tests	Acetaldehyde, Acetoin, Glycerol production	Bodegas Lustau S.L, Bodegas Caballero S.L.	(Ruiz-Muñoz et al., 2020)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> (Formerly <i>S. cerevisiae</i> var. <i>cheresiensis</i>)	2020	ScC, ScG	Jerez-Xères-Sherry (Jerez and El Puerto de Santa María)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance	RFLP-mtDNA, SSR-PCR, Interdelta elements PCR, D1/D2 PCR, Sequentiation, Fermentation and assimilation Carbon,	Acetaldehyde, Acetoin, Glycerol production	Bodegas Lustau S.L, Bodegas Caballero S.L.	(Ruiz-Muñoz et al., 2020)

						Nitrogen and other compound tests			
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	1997	1	La Rioja	Wine	Neutral phenotype Alcohol: 16% Temperature: 15-30°C Low production of foam, sulfurous and short chain fatty acids.	Biochemistry, RFLP-mtDNA	Increases varietal characteristics and ester content.	V22 / YES / Uvaferm VRB (Lallemand)	(Gutiérrez, 1995; Gutiérrez, López, & Santamaría, 1997; López et al., 1999)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	2007	1	La Rioja	Alcoholic fermentation	Neutral phenotype Alcohol: 15% Temperature: 18-32°C. High production of glycerol and polysaccharides	Biochemistry, RFLP-mtDNA	Increases the color of the wine, its roundness and smoothness.	ARG84 / YES / Zymaflore RJA64 (Laffort)	(López et al., 2007; Santamaría, 2009)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	1994	1	Madrid	Must fermentation	High fermentation performance; resistance to ethanol; low production of H ₂ S and SO ₂ ; high production of esters, ethyl hexanoate, ethyl octanoate and	PFGE, SSR-PCR, sequencing of D1/D2 region of the 26S rDNA gene	Fresh-fruity and flowery aroma	CLI 889	(Arroyo, 2000; Cordero-Bueso et al., 2016; García et al., 2016, 2020; García, Apolinar-Valiente, et al., 2017;

					2-phenylethyl acetate				García, Arroyo, et al., 2017; García, Esteve-Zarzoso, et al., 2017)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	1994	1	Madrid	Must fermentation	High consumption of amino acids precursors of oxidation notes	SSR-PCR	Reduction of oxidation aroma notes in organic wines	CLI 271	(Balboa-Lagunero et al., 2013)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	2009	1	Madrid	Must fermentation	Osmotic pressure, pH and ethanol resistance; esters and higher alcohols producer; wine yeast for functional beer elaboration	SSR-PCR	Sweet fruity and banana flavours in wine and beer	G 520	(García et al., 2016, 2019; Postigo et al., 2021; Tello et al., 2012)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	1995	325	Valdepeñas	wine Fermentation	Tolerate 30°Brix; 12% v/v; 100 ppm SO ₂ , Killer resistance	CHEF-PFGE Carbon fermentation tests. PCR ITS1-ITS2	Reinforce the structure of white wines while optimizing the expression of their varietal character.	SafCeno™ UCLM S325/Lesaffre	(Briones et al., 1995)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	1995	377	Valdepeñas	Wine Fermentation	Tolerate 30°Brix; 12% v/v; 100 ppm	CHEF-PFGE Carbon fermentation tests. PCR ITS1-ITS2	Produce very structured long	SafCeno™ UCLM S377/Lesaffre	(Briones et al., 1995)

					SO ₂ , Killer resistance		ageing and fruity red wines		
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	2013	G01, G04	Pago el Guijoso	wine fermentation	Killer resistance	RFLP-mtDNA PCR ITS1-ITS2	nd	Sánchez Muliterno cellar	(Fernández-González & Briones, 2013)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	2009-2011	2	Utiel-Requena	Fermenting Bobal, Cabernet-Sauvignon & Tempranillo grape must	Organic yeasts from organic vineyards and grapes	ITS sequencing, mtDNA	Fruity	55A, 110A	(Lucio et al., 2009; Polo et al., 2011)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	2015	5	Utiel-Requena	Fermenting Garnacha & Merlot grape must	Colour intensity (anthocyanins, tannins and phenolic compounds). Pleasant aroma: esters, 2-phenylethanol and γ -butyrolactone.	ITS sequencing, mtDNA	Colour intensity (anthocyanins, tannins and phenolic compounds). Pleasant aroma: esters, higher alcohols, and especially 2-phenylethanol and γ -butyrolactone.	22H, 2E, 4A, 7A, 7F	(Ut et al., 2021)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> (<i>beticus</i> , <i>montuliensis</i> , <i>cheresiensis</i> , <i>rouxii</i>)	2001; 2002		Jerez-Xèrés-Sherry (Jerez)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance	RFLP-mtDNA PCR ITS1-ITS2	n.d	González-Byass	(Aranda et al., 2002; Esteve-Zarzoso et al., 2001, 2004)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> (<i>beticus</i> , <i>montuliensis</i> ,	2013	B10, BS13, BS24, CH7, CH24,	Jerez-Xèrés-Sherry (Sanlúcar de Barrameda)	Manzanilla Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance	RFLP-mtDNA PCR ITS1-ITS2	n.d	Barbadillo S.L.	(Rodríguez et al., 2013)

<i>cheresiensis</i> , <i>rouxii</i>)		CHS15, B17							
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> var. <i>bayanus</i>	1982	1	Utiel- Requena	Fermenting Bobal grape must			Phenotypical tests		N7-2 (Pardo, 1987)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> var. <i>cerevisiae</i>	1982-83	3	Utiel- Requena	Fermenting Bobal grape must/Tempra nillo grape must			Phenotypical tests		AI-5, N8-1, TempI-1 (Pardo, 1987)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> : var <i>beticus</i>	1995; 1997	B2, B3, B16	Jerez-Xèrés- Sherry (Jerez)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance, Killer resistance		CHEF-PFGE mtDNA Carbon fermentation tests	Acetaldehyde production	Domecq S.A. (Martínez et al., 1995, 1997)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> : var <i>beticus</i> , <i>cheresiensis</i>	1999	III, A2, H2, R2, R3	Jerez-Xèrés- Sherry (Jerez)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance		CHEF-PFGE mtDNA Carbon fermentation tests	n.d.	Sandeman- Coprimar, S.A. (Mesa et al., 1999)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> : var <i>beticus</i> , <i>montuliensis</i> , <i>cheresiensis</i> , <i>rouxii</i>	1997	MY138, My91, CU2, ET7	Jerez-Xèrés- Sherry (El Puerto de Santa María)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance		CHEF-PFGE mtDNA Carbon fermentation tests	Acetaldehyde production	Osborne S.A. (Ibeas et al., 1997)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> : var <i>cheresiensis</i>	1995; 1997	CH16	Jerez-Xèrés- Sherry (Jerez)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance		CHEF-PFGE mtDNA Carbon fermentation tests	Acetaldehyde production	Domecq S.A. (Martínez et al., 1995, 1997)
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> : var <i>montuliensis</i>	1995; 1997	M9, M10, M12, M17	Jerez-Xèrés- Sherry (Jerez)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance, Killer resistance		CHEF-PFGE mtDNA Carbon fermentation tests	Acetaldehyde production	Domecq S.A. (Martínez et al., 1995, 1997)

<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> : var <i>rouxii</i>	1995; 1997	R13	Jerez-Xèrés-Sherry (Jerez)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance	CHEF-PFGE mtDNA Carbon fermentation tests	Acetaldehyde production	Domecq S.A.	(Martínez et al., 1995, 1997)
<i>Saccharomyces uvarum</i>	1982	1	Utiel-Requena	Bobal grape must		Phenotypical tests		BI-2	(Pardo, 1987)
<i>Schizosaccharomyces pombe</i>	1957	4	Córdoba	Grape and concentrated must	10-15% Ethanol, pyruvate, vitisin A		Demalication, structure, aroma, and colour	Promalic™ Proenol	(Loira et al., 2015; Morata et al., 2012; Palomero et al., 2009; Portugal et al., 2011; Rankine, 1966) https://www.proenol.com
<i>Schizosaccharomyces pombe</i>	2006	2	Madrid	Wine	Malic acid metabolism; volatile acidity reduction; elevated ethanol production and resistance; β-phenylethyl alcohol producer	Selective media: LYS/WL, PCR-RFLP of 5.8S ITS region, sequencing of D1/D2 region of the 26S rDNA gene	Fruity aroma	CLI 1085 & CLI 1079	(Cordero-Bueso et al., 2013; García et al., 2016, 2021; García, Arroyo, et al., 2017; García, Esteve-Zarzoso, et al., 2017)
<i>Torulaspora delbrueckii</i>	2015	2	Extremadura	Vineyard	Fermentation vigour, killer Kbar	Selective media, biochemistry, gene sequencing	Dried fruit/pastry aromas	EX1180, EX1257	(Ramírez et al., 2016;

					phenotype, low volatile acidity		Promote malolactic fermentation		Velázquez et al., 2015, 2019)
<i>Torulaspora delbrueckii</i>	2006	1	Madrid	Wine	High ethanol producer (10.88%, v/v); glycerol producer; MPs-releasing in pure and sequential cultures; β -phenylethyl alcohol, ethyl hexanoate, and 2-phenylethyl acetate producer	Selective media: LYS/WL, PCR-RFLP of 5.8S ITS region, sequencing of D1/D2 region of the 26S rDNA gene	Flowery and fruity aroma notes, full-bodied wines	CLI 918	(Cordero-Bueso et al., 2013; García, Apolinar-Valiente, et al., 2017; García, Arroyo, et al., 2017; García, Esteve-Zaroso, et al., 2017)
<i>Torulaspora delbrueckii</i>	2009	W37	La Mancha	Wine fermentation		PCR ITS1-ITS2	lower levels of volatile acidity		(Barrajón et al., 2009, 2011)
<i>Torulaspora delbrueckii</i>	1983	3	Utiel-Requena	Bobal, Garnacha & Cabernet-Sauvignon grape musts		Phenotypical tests		BoIII-5, GarI-5, CSI-5	(Pardo, 1987)
<i>Torulaspora delbrueckii</i>	2015	1	Utiel-Requena	Fermenting Cabernet-Sauvignon, Garnacha & Merlot grape musts	Good coexistence with <i>S. cerevisiae</i>	ITS sequencing, mtDNA	Sweeter tasting (no residual sugar), good palatability, lower astringency	58E	(Morillas Álvarez, 2020)

<i>Torulaspora delbrueckii/ L. thermotolerans</i> 70/30	2020	2 (mixed inoculum)	La Rioja	Alcoholic fermentation	For use in sequential inoculation with <i>S. cerevisiae</i> . High production of lactic acid (> 3g/L), ethyl lactate (> 20mg/L) and glycerol (>10g/L)	Amplification of D1/D2 by PCR. Sequencing in Macrogen Inc. Characterized at clonal level by RAPD-PCR	Increase the acidity of the wine. Provides smoothness, sweetness, complexity and pleasant aromas.	LT1 (ICVV collection)/ NO	(Escribano-Viana et al., 2018, 2021; Escribano-Viana, Garijo, et al., 2019; Escribano-Viana, Portu, et al., 2019; Escribano et al., 2018)
<i>Wickerhamomyces anomalus</i>	2007	1	Madrid	Grape	Ethanol content reduction (0.9%, v/v); High β -glucosidase activity; esters and β -phenylethyl alcohol production	Selective media: LYS/WL, PCR-RFLP of 5.8S ITS region, sequencing of D1/D2 region of the 26S rDNA gene	Fruity and floral aroma compounds	21A-5C	(Arroyo et al., 2010; García et al., 2020)
<i>Wickerhamomyces anomalus</i> (formerly <i>Pichia anomala</i>)	2001	n.d.	Jerez-Xèrés-Sherry (Jerez)	Sobretablas Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance	RFLP-mtDNA PCR ITS1-ITS2	n.d	González-Byass	(Esteve-Zarzoso et al., 2001)
<i>Wickerhamomyces anomalus</i> (formerly <i>Pichia anomala</i>)	2020	NsB	Jerez-Xèrés-Sherry (Jerez and El Puerto de Santa María)	Fino Sherry wine	15,5% etOH resistance	RFLP-mtDNA, SSR-PCR, Interdelta elements PCR, D1/D2 PCR, Sequentiation,	n.d	Bodegas Lustau S.L, Bodegas Caballero S.L.	(Ruiz-Muñoz et al., 2020)

						Fermentation and assimilation Carbon, Nitrogen and other compound tests			
<i>Wickerhamomyces anomalus</i> (formerly <i>Pichia anomala</i>)	1982	3	Utiel-Requena	Bobal grape must		Phenotypical tests		BI-3 CI-1 GI-1	(Pardo, 1987)

Table 2. Percentage of acetic acid (*italic letters*) and glucose (**bold letters**) consumption after refermentation of wine-supplemented culture medium, containing glucose 13% (w/v) and ethanol 4% (v/v) or glucose 3.3% (w/v) and ethanol 10% (v/v), after 48 and 72 h of incubation, respectively.

	Glucose (13%, w/v) Ethanol (4%, v/v)		Glucose (3.3%, w/v) Ethanol (10%, v/v)	
	Aerobic Conditions	Limited Aerobic Conditions	Aerobic Conditions	Limited Aerobic Conditions
Yeast strains	<i>Acetic acid</i> Glucose	<i>Acetic acid</i> Glucose	<i>Acetic acid</i> Glucose	<i>Acetic acid</i> Glucose
<i>L. thermotolerans</i> 44C	94.6 ± 4.79 58.5 ± 8.60 c	15.25 ± 3.30 31.0 ± 5.69	28.1 ± 1.70 16.4 ± 1.76	17.4 ± 7.16 30.4 ± 5.79
<i>S. cerevisiae</i> 43C	0 ± 0 100 ± 0	31.2 ± 9.70 96.94 ± 3.17	36.4 ± 9.88 40.7 ± 7.42	37.5 ± 3.17 100 ± 0
<i>S. cerevisiae</i> 45C	16.0 ± 4.06 100 ± 0	40.3 ± 6.60 97.4 ± 2.28	33.4 ± 6.88 23.8 ± 6.61	40.1 ± 6.58 100 ± 0

Figure 1. Yeast strains selections in several Iberian wine regions. The area of circles is proportional to the number of selected strains. Sc: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, Scby: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* var. bayanus, Scb: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* var. beticus, Scm: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* var. montuliensis, Scch: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* var. cheresiensis, Scr: *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* var. rouxii, Scu: *Saccharomyces uvarum*, Cp: *Candida pulcherrima*, Cs: *Candida stellata*, Ho: *Hanseniaspora opuntiae*, Hu: *Hanseniaspora uvarum*, Ka: *Kloeckera apis*, Kj: *Kloeckera japonica*, Lf: *Lachancea fermentati*, Lt: *Lachancea thermotolerans*, Mf: *Metschnikowia fructicola*, Mp: *Metschnikowia pulcherrima*, Mg: *Meyerozyma guilliermondii*, Pf: *Pichia fermentans*, Pk: *Pichia kluyveri*, Pkd: *Pichia kudriavzevii*, Pm: *Pichia manshurica*, Pme: *Pichia membranaefaciens*, Pt: *Pichia terricola*, Sp: *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*, Sb: *Starmerella bacillaris*, Td: *Torulaspora delbrueckii*, Wa: *Wickerhamomyces anomalus*. Madeira Islands are not located in the real geographic position.

Figure 2. Phylogenetic tree with main non-*Saccharomyces* isolated in grapes from Jerez, Uclés, La Mancha, and Ribera del Duero regions. The main enological impact is indicated in some of the non-*Saccharomyces* species. Species: *Lachancea thermotolerans*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Zygosaccharomyces bisporus*, *Zygosaccharomyces baillii*, *Pichia kudriavzevii*, *Pichia manshurica*, *Candida stellimalicola*, *Metschnikowia pulcherrima*, *Starmerella bacillaris*, *Saccharomycopsis fibuligera*, *Aureobasidium melanogenum*, *Aureobasidium pullulans*, *Vishniacozyma tephrensensis*, *Rhodotorula mucilaginosa*, *Naganishia uzbekistanensis*, *Naganishia adeliensis*, *Filobasidium chernovii*, *Filobasidium oeirensis*, *Hanseniaspora uvarum*, *Hanseniaspora opuntiae*, *Hanseniaspora guilliermondii*.

Figure 3. Yeast selection processes of several strains of the species *Lachancea thermotolerans* from grape to pilot and industrial fermentation as liquid cultures and dried yeast. Also, it is shown the industrial performance for wine acidification compared with the commercial strains Laktia™ and Concerto™ (Vaquero et al., 2020).

A

B

Figure 4. A - Yeast isolates from a refermentation process (dilution of 10^{-3} cell/mL) in WL medium, showing characteristic colony colour and morphologies: cream (A1), green (A2), and small green (A3) colonies are probably *S. cerevisiae* isolates; intense green colonies (B) belong to *Hanseniaspora uvarum*/*Kloeckera apiculata* species; cream colonies with a hint of green (C) to *Torulasporea delbrueckii* and small cream colonies (D) are isolates of *Zygosaccharomyces bailii*, according to Pallmann et al. (2001). B- Growth and colour change (due to pH changes) of differential medium (Schuller et al., 2000) with 0.5% (v/v) acetic acid, 0.05% (w/v) glucose, and bromocresol green (0.005% (w/v)) at pH 4.0, indicating the simultaneous consumption of glucose and acetic acid by the isolated strains, namely “44C”. E: *S. cerevisiae* PYCC4072 (negative control); F: *Z. bailii* ISA1307 (positive control). Retrieved from Vilela et al. (Vilela et al., 2015).

Supplementary Figure 1

Supplementary Figure S1. Dendrogram built from the mtDNA digested with HinfI of 64 isolates identified as *S. cerevisiae*. The analysis is based on the similarities of the restriction profiles using the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient and the unweighted pair group method with arithmetic mean (UPGMA). Different colours show different profiles assimilated to different strains.